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‘A FARE-FREE PRINCIPLE’:
THE HISTORY AND DEVELOPMENT OF FARE-
FREE PUBLIC TRANSPORT IN IKAST-BRANDE,
DENMARK

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1. Introduction

This report examines the history of fare-free public transport (FFPT) in the Danish municipality Ikast-Brande.¹ This is often referred to as the municipality's "fare-free principle" ("gratis princippet").² The report details the origins of the fare-free principle and identifies significant issues in its development. The research has been conducted on behalf of the project "From Low Fares to No Fares: An Analysis of Economic, Operational, Socio-Spatial and Political Dynamics of Fare-Free Public Transport" (LiFT).³ More specifically, the report is the outcome of a questionnaire forwarded to a representative of the Ikast-Brande municipality. The questionnaire was part of a larger survey that looked to gather information about FFPT practices around the world: their sizes, natures, finances and histories. It was returned largely unanswered by Ikast-Brande, and I was engaged by LiFT to help find answers to the questions ignored by the municipality.

The report is not conclusive. It has not been possible to find all the information requested by LiFT in the circulated questionnaire. For example, the report does not include more than sporadic information about budgets and passenger numbers. But it does clarify a number of other key issues. For example, it has been possible to create a reasonably clear picture of when FFPT was introduced in the municipality and under what circumstances. The reasons behind the introduction and continued existence of the FFPT system are evident too. The report also provides information about the size of the FFPT system and how it is (and has been)

administered in relation other public transport (PT) networks in the country.

The report continues with a discussion of the methods and materials on which the research is based (Section 2). It then gives a brief introduction to the Ikast-Brande municipality (Section 3) and the current extent of its FFPT system (Section 4). Section 5 explains how the municipality came to have FFPT, detailing the circumstances that led to its introduction and continued development. Section 6 discusses the municipality's fare-free principle from several different perspectives: political and administrative; economic; social; environmental; and influence and applicability. The report's findings are summarised in the conclusion (Section 7).

2. Methods and Materials

This section provides a brief discussion of the methods and materials used in the report. The material consists primarily of Danish newspaper articles and notices published between 1994 and 2022. These were collected using the Royal Danish Library's digital newspaper databases *Infomedia* and *Mediastream*.⁴ More specifically, searches were made in these databases and relevant keywords were used to delimit the results.⁵ The collected articles and notices stem from local newspapers (e.g. *Herning Folkeblad* and *Midtjyllands Avis*) as well as national ones (e.g. *Politiken*, *Berlingske*, *Jyllands-Posten*). There are also articles from the websites of the national broadcasting corporations, *Danmarks Radio* and *TV2*. Of the 255 articles gathered, many focus directly on the FFPT system in Ikast-

¹ The report builds on the following definition of FFPT: "It highlights the absence of tickets or distribution of zero-fare tickets as the principal and unique characteristic of the policy, and accentuates that fares are "free" only because they are fully subsidised" (Wojciech Kębłowski, "Why (Not) Abolish Fares? Exploring the Global Geography of Fare-Free Public Transport", *Transportation* 47 (2019), 2807-2835, here 2809. doi.org/10.1007/s11116-019-09986-6.)

² This phrase has been used to describe the system since its inception (e.g. *Midtjyllands Avis*, "Fortsat Gratis-Bus og Steward i Ikast", 8 February 1996, 18). Later in the report (Section 6), I speculate on its meaning and use. All translations in the report are by the author.

³ For more about LiFT, see its website: www.freepublictransport.net.

⁴ *Infomedia* is an electronic database of Danish newspapers from 1990 to the present. *Mediastream* has newspapers from 1666 to 2013. For more information, see the website of the Royal Danish Library: www.kb.dk.

⁵ The keywords used were "Ikast gratis kollektiv trafik" ("Ikast free public transport"), "Ikast gratis busser" ("Ikast free busses") and "gratis busser" ("free buses").

(Brande).⁶ But a sizeable portion is concerned with other places in Denmark or simply aim to discuss the topic of FFPT in general. In these cases, it is typical that the FFPT system in Ikast(-Brande) is at least briefly mentioned. In addition to these articles and notices, it is worth highlighting the report “Traffic in the Countryside and to the Small Islands” (“Trafikken på Landet og til de Små Øer”) published by the Ministry of Traffic in 1997.⁷ It provided a partial evaluation of the nationwide transportation trials that led to the introduction of FFPT in the old Ikast municipality and it gave valuable contextual information to the collected newspaper materials.

Initially, the collected material was analysed chronologically. That method was chosen because one important aim of the report is to establish the history of FFPT in Ikast(-Brande). The main results of that analysis can be found in Section 5. However, the chronological perspective does not disappear entirely afterwards. Although Section 6 is primarily a thematic discussion, it mainly focuses on the period after the introduction and establishment of FFPT in the municipality and does so in a largely chronological fashion. The perspectives focused on in Section 6 were not decided upon prior to investigation, but arose organically from the analyses of the collected material. Before proceeding to discuss what these analyses revealed, it is necessary to say a few things in general about the Ikast-Brande municipality and its FFPT system.

3. Ikast-Brande Municipality

This section serves as an introduction to Ikast-Brande, providing some basic information about the municipality relevant to the study of its FFPT system. It situates Ikast-Brande in its current national and regional context, but also looks back to the 2007 municipal reform, a significant event in the history of the municipality’s FFPT system.

Ikast-Brande is located in the middle Jutland – for a period, the municipal slogan was “In the Heart of Jutland” (“I Hjertet af Jylland”) – and covers an area of 733.50 km² (Figure 1).⁸ It has a population of 42,540 which gives the municipality a population density of fifty-eight citizens per square kilometre. 83.4 per cent of the population lives in urban settlements (“bymæssig bebyggelse”) and the largest cities are Ikast (15,979), Brande (7,449), Bording (2,389), Engesvang (2,060) and Nørre Snede (1,932) (Figure 2).⁹

On a national level, Ikast-Brande ranks in the middle when it comes to population size and the number of people to live in urban settlements.¹⁰ It falls just outside the upper fifth in terms of area while its population density is among the lowest in the country.¹¹

Slightly unusual for Denmark, Ikast-Brande has no coastline and is surrounded by seven other municipalities: Viborg, Silkeborg, Horsens, Hedensted, Vejle, Billund and Herning (Figure 1). Compared to these, Ikast-Brande relatively small and thinly populated. Horsens, Billund

⁶ As will be discussed, the Ikast-Brande municipality was formed during the municipal reform in 2007 out of the old Ikast, Brande and Nørre Snede municipalities. The FFPT system stretches back to the old Ikast municipality. Occasionally, it is necessary to refer to the FFPT system as it exists now and as it was prior to the establishment of the new municipality. I use the spelling “Ikast(-Brande)” in such cases.

⁷ *Trafikministeriet*, “Trafikken på Landet og til de Små Øer”, 9 May 1997 <https://www.trm.dk/media/ja415q0o/trafikken-paa-landet-og-til-de-smaa-oeerpdf.pdf> (accessed 30 May 2024). In 2006, the Ministry of Traffic became the Ministry of Transport and Energy. In 2007, the name changed again to the Ministry of Transport. That is the name today.

⁸ This section draws on statistics from the Danish Ministry of Interior and Health, see: www.noegletal.dk. The Ministry of Interior and Health takes its figure from Statistics Denmark, see www.dst.dk. The figures used here are from 2022 and gathered on 16 May 2023.

⁹ Statistics Denmark defines “bymæssig bebyggelse” as “number of citizens in cities with 200 inhabitants or more in percent of the municipality’s total number of inhabitant on 1 January” (www.noegletal.dk).

¹⁰ There are ninety-eight municipalities in Denmark. In terms of population size, Ikast-Brande is number fifty-three; in terms of people living in urban settlements, it is number fifty.

¹¹ It is the twenty-first largest municipality in the country. When it comes to population density, it ranks eighty-one.

Figure 1. Map of Danish municipalities. Municipalities and cities relevant for the present discussion have been highlighted. Ikast-Brande is marked in the darkest shade. Also highlighted are the boundaries of the Central Denmark Region (“Region Midtjylland”). All annotations are by the author. Source: Wikimedia Commons.

Figure 2. Map of the Ikast-Brande municipality. Cities relevant for the present discussion have been highlighted. All annotations are by the author. Source: Wikimedia Commons.

and Hedensted cover a smaller area while Ikast-Brande only surpasses Billund in terms of population size and density. Concerning people to live in urban settlements, Ikast-Brande has more than Billund, Viborg and Hedensted. Looking only at these municipalities, Ikast is the sixth largest city and Brande number nine, but the most important cities nearby are significantly larger: Viborg (41,239), Silkeborg (49,747), Horsens (61,074), Vejle (60,231) and Herning (50,565). In addition, Denmark's second largest city, Århus (355,238), is only about sixty kilometres to the east.

Administratively, above the municipal level, Ikast-Brande belongs to the Central Denmark Region ("Region Midtjylland") as do Herning, Viborg, Silkeborg, Horsens, Hedensted and thirteen other municipalities while Billund and Vejle to the south fall under the Region of Southern Denmark ("Region Syddanmark") (Figure 1). From a PT perspective, this is significant because, in Denmark, PT tends to be organised at the regional level. But, as will be discussed, this is a flexible system which has allowed certain municipalities, including Ikast-Brande, to retain control of their PT system.

In 2007, Denmark's administrative landscape changed radically. The municipal reform that came into effect that year is a significant event in the history of Ikast-Brande and its FFPT system. The reform introduced a large-scale reorganisation of the public sector. In short, it divided the country into larger units. Whereas before Denmark had consisted of 271 municipalities grouped into thirteen so-called "amter", it now had ninety-eight municipalities grouped into five "regions". Ikast-Brande was formed at this time out of the old Ikast, Brande and Nørre Snede municipalities. The current FFPT system originates in the old Ikast municipality. It was allowed to continue in the new larger municipality, although, as will be discussed, this was not a foregone conclusion.

4. FFPT in Ikast-Brande

This section provides an overview of Ikast-Brande's current PT system. According to the definitions developed by Kębłowski (2019), Ikast-Brande has a "partial" FFPT system, bordering on a "full." That is to say, the system is "implemented on the vast majority of routes and services provided" and is "available to the vast majority of its users, most of the time" but it is "socially-limited."¹² Since 2016, two of the municipality's bus routes have been so-called "closed routes" ("lukkede ruter"). These will be discussed later.

In short, apart from the two closed routes, PT within the municipality is fare-free while that which crosses municipal boundaries is not. The reason for this has to do with how PT is organised in Denmark. In connection with the municipal reform in 2007, the Danish PT system was reorganised. Each of the country's six regions got its own PT company responsible for organising PT throughout the region in collaboration with local municipalities. In the Central Denmark Region, for example, the company Midttrafik was established.¹³ It runs a large number of regional bus services as well as train lines and, partly, the light rail in Århus. It also manages PT in several municipalities, but in some, including Ikast-Brande, it does not. In Ikast-Brande, the municipal council manages PT within the municipality, overseeing a number of city and local bus routes. It is these bus services that are fare free. Those run by Midttrafik are not.

At the time of writing, the FFPT network in Ikast-Brande consists of three city bus lines that, primarily, run in the urban area of Ikast, the municipality's largest city.¹⁴ In addition, there are nineteen local bus routes. Some of these link Ikast to the surrounding area, including the other large cities in the municipality, Brande, Bording, Nørre Snede and Engesvang. Others run entirely in other parts of the municipality. All routes are fare-free for all except the two closed routes. These only accept school children.

¹² Kębłowski, "Why (Not) Abolish Fares?", 2810.

¹³ For more on Midttrafik, see www.midttrafik.dk.

¹⁴ On PT in Ikast-Brande, see <https://ikast-brande.dk/borger/teknik-og-miljoe/trafik-og-veje/kollektivtrafik#lokalruter-gratis-72>.

The city bus lines are all circle lines, starting and ending in the same place, Ikast's main square, and the number of trips per day is limited. Two of the lines run six times per day between seven in the morning and three in the afternoon while the third only runs three times in the same period, once on a slightly different route. None of the lines run during weekends and holidays.

The nineteen local bus routes operate throughout the municipality. Characteristic of all nineteen routes is that they are primarily organised around the municipality's legal obligation to provide school transport for children in the area, the universal service obligation ("forsyningspligten"). (This obligation is important for understanding the city's FFPT system and will be discussed in more detail in the following section.) Common for all is that they only run on schooldays. This is clearly indicated in the timetables where it is also specified which periods during the coming year constitute schooldays. It is implied that there is no service on weekends and during public holidays unless it coincides with official school activities. During the week, services are also clearly organised around school schedules. Most routes have a morning run followed by a pause until there is about three or four departures in the early afternoon. The majority of the routes stop running after three or four p.m. Only four routes continue in the evening (last runs between nine and ten p.m.). These all link Brande Station with various other parts of the municipality. The requirement to provide school children with transport is also discernible in the routes. Most often, the start and end points are schools, sports halls and other educational facilities as are other highlighted locations in the timetables. Other notable characteristics of the nineteen local bus routes is that some routes are only serviced at certain times if there are passengers to drop off and some departures are explicitly linked to the arrival of certain other lines. Presumably, both regulations are linked to the requirements of the area's school children.

As mentioned, two of the local routes are so-called "closed routes". These are fare-free, but only accept school children as passengers. It is due to them that the Ikast-Brande FFPT system can be said to be only "partial."¹⁵ However, as will be discussed later (Section 6), these restrictions appear to be a response to social problems in the municipality rather than a wish to rethink the FFPT system and take it in a new direction.

5. The Origins of FFPT in Ikast-Brande

5.1 Testing a Partial FFPT System, 1994-1995

The background for the introduction of FFPT in the old Ikast municipality is a series of nationwide trials of municipal transportation solutions that ran between 1992-1995. These tests were initiated and supported by the Ministry of Traffic ("Trafikministeriet") with the aim of finding "attractive and economically efficient service forms in areas with little or varying needs."¹⁶ In other words, the tests focused on solving certain problems associated with the organisation of PT in rural and thinly populated municipalities. Primarily, these problems were associated with the universal service obligation.¹⁷ In Denmark, then as well as now, municipalities are legally obliged to provide free transportation for specific groups of people, for specific purposes.¹⁸ These include, for example:

- Transportation of schoolchildren between home and school, swimming lessons and confirmation preparation;
- Transportation of senior citizens to and from care homes and day centres;
- Transportation to visit doctors and hospitals;
- Transportation for the disabled;
- Meal transportation.

¹⁵ Kębłowski, "Why (Not) Abolish Fares?", 2810.

¹⁶ *Trafikministeriet*, "Trafikken på Landet", 109.

¹⁷ *Trafikministeriet*, "Trafikken på Landet", 106.

¹⁸ *Trafikministeriet*, "Trafikken på Landet", 106.

In the early 1990s, these services tended to be organised in different municipal departments, individually without cross-departmental cooperation.¹⁹ One aim of the trials was to examine through practical application whether centralised coordination could be financially beneficial without loss in the quality of the overall service. Another had to do with the organisation of local, municipal PT networks and the requirements entailed in the universal service obligation.

Often, rural and thinly populated municipalities maintained a PT network consisting of a limited number of bus routes running according to specific and restricted timetables. The primary function of these networks was to fulfil the part of universal service obligation that concerns school children: they were free for the children while others had to pay a fare, and they tended to be geographically organised around schools and other educational facilities. Such networks tended to have greatly varying passenger numbers. At certain hours of the day, before and after school, the burden was heavy. Outside these times, the demand was too minute and too geographically scattered to make it financially viable to maintain regular service.²⁰ The result was that passengers not covered by the universal service obligation and without access to a private car were often left in the lurch. In addition, PT was a highly unattractive alternative for citizens with access to a private car.²¹ An aim of the trials was, then, to explore ways of improving existing PT networks by integrating them with the other requirements entailed in the universal service obligation.²² In addition, it was to be tested if such integration could also improve the service for citizens outside the universal service obligation and make PT a more attractive alternative for car owners. In this latter respect, the tests had

clearly articulated, although secondary, environmental and sustainability aims.²³

Between 1992 and 1995, the Ministry of Traffic supported about sixty-five projects.²⁴ Of these, thirty focused on PT in certain municipalities and twenty-one were put into practical tests. In May 1997, thirteen of the trials had continued after the end of the trial period. As mentioned, the focus was on rural and thinly populated areas, including some islands. Geographically, the trial areas represented all parts of Denmark. The trials shared the common *raison d'être* described above, but the specific nature of the trials varied from municipality to municipality. Some focused on centralisation and integration of the universal service obligation in the administration; some tested more flexible PT services (e.g. telebuses and taxis); some tried making it easier to bring a bicycle on board PT; some ran trials with stewards and helpers on board busses; while others tested different fare initiatives. Among the latter was a test with a partial FFPT system in Ikast.²⁵

In 1997, the Ministry of Traffic published a report entitled “Traffic in the Countryside and to the Small Islands” which presented a partial evaluation to Parliament of the transportation trials that had run between 1992-1995. The report gave the following succinct summary of the trials in the Ikast municipality:

During the trial with transport coordination in the Ikast municipality, the transportation services paid for by the municipality such as school- and youth-transportation, swimming transportation, doctor transportation and care centre transportation (done with bus, taxi and Falck) were coordinated with local

¹⁹ *Trafikministeriet*, “Trafikken på Landet”, 107.

²⁰ *Trafikministeriet*, “Trafikken på Landet”, 108.

²¹ One problem was that PT often ran along main and country roads, and did not service municipal centres (*Trafikministeriet*, “Trafikken på Landet”, 108).

²² *Trafikministeriet*, “Trafikken på Landet”, 108.

²³ *Trafikministeriet*, “Trafikken på Landet”, 153-164.

²⁴ For an overview of the projects, see *Trafikministeriet*, “Trafikken på Landet”, 171-172.

²⁵ The title of the project in Ikast was “Transport Coordination in Ikast Municipality” (“Transportkoordinering i Ikast Kommune”) (*Trafikministeriet*, “Trafikken på Landet”, 171). It seems that a partial FFPT system was also tested in Nysted on Lolland in 1995. Contrary to Ikast, however, this seems only to have concerned one specific telebus route (*Trafikministeriet*, “Trafikken på Landet”, 171).

public transport, consisting of fixed local bus lines and one city bus line.

Besides fixed transportation to and from schools, the trial consists of telebus transportation, including door-to-door service, and offers to schools, institutions and clubs for the elderly for order- and tourist-transportation. In addition, the trial includes a fare test where all public transport is free after 8 a.m. During the trial, a new low-floor minibus was introduced in the city that was manned with a steward whose task was to assist during entering and exiting and in case of short distances between bus and final destination.²⁶

To this it can be added that the trials with FFPT was initiated in connection with the renewal of the five-year tender for PT in the municipality and that the initial trial was for one year, from start of the 1994-1995 timetable on 8 August till the following July.²⁷ The fare-free trials included the normal route-bound buses as well as the telebus service.²⁸ As is clear from the quote above, it was a partial (and not a full) FFPT system that was tested. The buses were only fare-free outside the morning rush hour. In addition, transportation was only fare-free on certain routes on school days while the city bus in Ikast was free on other days as well.²⁹ Moreover, the fare-free system did not cover the whole municipality. It was restricted to services covering the cities of Ikast, Isenvad and Tulstrup-Fauerholt, leaving, for instance, senior citizens in Engesvang uncovered (Figure 2).³⁰

It is unclear why, specifically, the Ikast municipality was chosen as a site for testing FFPT, but there were certain circumstances that made it suitable. Before discussing these it must

be noted, however, that the trials were not structured in a top-down manner. The Ministry of Traffic did not dictate which places should run which trials. Rather, it was done in collaboration with the municipalities through an application system. Whether the idea of testing FFPT in Ikast originated in the municipality or somewhere else is uncertain, but it is clear that there were certain circumstances which made it easier to do in Ikast than in other places. First, in the mid-1990s, there were essentially three different ways of organising PT at municipal and regional levels.³¹ The capital area had its own special way. (For the present discussion, this is not relevant). In eight out of the eleven “amter” outside the capital area, all PT was handled by joint municipal traffic companies. In the remaining three (Fyns Amt, Århus Amt and Ringkjøbing Amt), PT between the municipalities was organised by the “amt” while local PT within the municipalities were handled by the municipalities themselves. As Harry Lahrman, a transport scholar, pointed out after the FFPT trial in Ikast had concluded, it was less complicated to introduce FFPT in “amter” where the municipalities held control over PT inside their own borders than in “amter” where it was organised through joint municipal traffic companies.³² Second, the fact that the tender for PT in the municipality was up for renewal in 1994 might have meant that it was easier to initiate a new trial and get that written into the deal with the contractors. There were felicitous conditions, but why Ikast was chosen – or put itself forward for such a test – is unclear.

Although it is unclear why Ikast was chosen as a site for testing FFPT, it is clear that the trial was quickly a success. Already in October 1994, there were reports of an increase in

²⁶ *Trafikministeriet*, “Trafikken på Landet”, 160.

²⁷ *Herning Folkeblad*, “Ikast Klar til Forsøg med Gratis Bybus-Kørsel”, 28 April 1994, 1; *Midtjyllands Avis*, “Engesvang Turistfart Vandt Lokal Busrute Tilbage”, 30 April 1994, 23.

²⁸ *Herning Folkeblad*, “Gratis med Bybussen”, 23 February 1995, 7.

²⁹ *Herning Folkeblad*, “Gratis med Bybussen.”

³⁰ *Midtjyllands Avis*, “Ønsker om Pensionist-Busser”, 25 November 1994, 21; *Midtjyllands Avis*, “Fortsat Gratis-Bus og Steward i Ikast.”

³¹ *Trafikministeriet*, “Trafikken på Landet”, 103-104.

³² Lahrman was cited in Rune Huvendick Jensen, “Kommune Sparer ved Gratis Kørsel”, *Politiken* 16 February 1998, 5. Similar points were made elsewhere at the time. See, for example: Torben Arent, “Gratis Bus Kan Spredde Sig”, *Berlingske* 1 February 1998, 9.

passenger numbers exceeding expectations, with especially the number of children and elderly having risen.³³ These were repeated at the beginning of 1995. In February, for example, the front page of *Herning Folkeblad* declared the fare-free buses to be “a thundering success” and the headline of the newspaper’s feature article said the system was “almost too popular.”³⁴ As the trial was nearing its conclusion, the positive vibes did not diminish. In May 1995, Niels Peter Mohr, then planner in the city’s technical department (“teknisk forvaltning”), was widely quoted as saying that the FFPT system had caused passenger numbers to increase with twenty-five percent and had “caused many citizens to leave the car at home.”³⁵ When, eventually, the trial was evaluated, Mohr proved too cautious in his first assessment and too optimistic in the second.

In late autumn 1995, *Herning Folkeblad* reported that the official evaluation of the trial concluded the fare-free system to be a success.³⁶ Although it had not caused citizens to leave the car at home, as Mohr had claimed, there had been a number of positive effects. The report noted an eighty-four per cent increase in passenger numbers (contrast Mohr’s twenty-five per cent estimate), mainly among children and the elderly. There was a high level of satisfaction with the fare-free system and the low floor buses. Although the savings had not been as high as expected, the costs had dropped by 88,000 DKK, including support from the Ministry of Traffic. The low savings, it was

claimed, was mainly due to the need for a ticketing system during the rush hour. Arguably, the most notable sign of the FFPT system’s success was that the municipal authorities led it continue for the 1995-1996 timetable with the proviso that the system could be changed once the official report had been evaluated.³⁷

There were also problems, but these had less to do with the principles of the system than its limitations. For example, there were complaints coming from Engesvang where the fare-free initiative had failed to make an impact because there were no buses outside the rush hour.³⁸ People there would like a fare-free option too. It was also reported that, during the trial, many citizens had not been aware of the initiative and, finally, there was the question of the system’s continuation.³⁹ The satisfaction was widespread, but would it be possible to make the partial FFPT system permanent?⁴⁰ The short answer is yes – plus it was also possible to move on to full FFPT. But, as will be discussed in the following section, certain conditions had to be met before it could happen.

5.2 Expansion to Full FFPT, 1996-1998

Following the successful trial of a partial FFPT system from August 1994 to July 1995, the municipal authorities decided to continue the initiative for the following year, pending the results of the evaluation of the trial. As discussed above, the official report was

³³ *Ritzau*, “Forsøg med Gratis Buskørsel Er en Stor Succes”, 26 October 1994; *Midtjyllands Avis*, “Service på Bussen”, 27 October 1994, 20.

³⁴ *Herning Folkeblad*, “Næsten for Populær”, 23 February 1995, 7. A minor notice to the same effect was brought in *Berlingske*, “Gratis Busser en Stor Succes”, 25 February 1995, 2. The same notice also appeared in *Lemvig Folkeblad*, *Dagbladet Holstebro-Struer*, *Ringkjøbing Amts Dagblad* and *Ritzau* on the same day.

³⁵ *Herning Folkeblad*, “Gratis med Bybussen.” Mohr’s assessment was also brought in *Ritzau*, “Gratisbusser Er Blevet en Succes”, 4 May 1995. On the following day, the same notice was published in *Fredericia Dagblad*, *Politiken*, *Jyllands-Posten*, *Næstved Tidende* and *Sjællands Tidende*.

³⁶ *Herning Folkeblad*, “Gratis-Busser Fik Ikke Folk til at Droppe Bilen”, 11 November 1995, 9. The article states that the official evaluation was made by an Århus-based company called “Advance 1.” It has not been possible to obtain a copy of the evaluation.

³⁷ When, later, the Ministry of Traffic compiled its report “Trafikken på landet og til de små øer” (“Traffic in the Countryside and to the Small Islands”), it concluded the trials to have been a success (*Trafikministeriet*, “Trafikken på Landet”, 160).

³⁸ *Midtjyllands Avis*, “Ønsker om Pensionist-Busser.”

³⁹ *Herning Folkeblad*, “Næsten for Populær.”

⁴⁰ In February 1995, this was reported to be an open question. See, for example: *Berlingske*, “Gratis Busser en Stor Succes.” As noted above, this notice was published in several other newspapers on the same day.

positive, largely confirming the impressions of people working in the municipality and, therefore, it was not deemed necessary to make changes to the system between August 1995 and July 1996. In preparation for the next timetable (August 1996 to July 1997), it was discussed within the municipality whether the partial FFPT system should be made permanent, even without support from the Ministry of Traffic. By February 1996, it was reported that the municipal authorities had decided to make the partial FFPT system permanent.⁴¹ The conclusion was that the system was economically feasible, allowing the municipality to save money on transportation. As then mayor Kjeld Broberg Lind said,

The municipality's fare-free policy is not about ideology for or against user fees. It has simply turned out that the missing income from tickets on bus departures after the morning departures is outweighed by the increase in number of passengers when it's possible to ride for free, and by the fact that more elderly people are now taking the bus instead of more expensive options paid for by the municipality.⁴²

And, not only would the system be made permanent, it would also expand to cover the whole municipality, including the cities of Bording and Engesvang.

In the spring of 1996, it was also discussed whether the system could not be converted to full FFPT. At that time, it was not considered feasible. Extending the system so it was also fare free during the rush hour required negotiations with Ringkjøbing Amt, particularly in relation to the fare structures of the regional PT services. There were also

concerns about whether a full FFPT system would lead to capacity problems during the rush hour.⁴³ In the autumn of 1997, however, the question of full FFPT was taken up again. It was reported in *Midtjyllands Avis* that the technical and environmental committee ("teknik- og miljøudvalget") in Ikast would propose to Ringkjøbing Amt that the last fares on buses within the municipality were dropped.⁴⁴ The reasoning: it was too complicated and costly to collect fares and, if fares were to be collected continuously, the ticket machines would need to be replaced at significant cost. It was cheaper to not renew the ticketing machines and drop fares altogether.

By autumn 1997, the proposal to transfer to full FFPT still needed to be approved by, first, the municipal council and, then, by Ringkjøbing Amt.⁴⁵ Already at the beginning of 1998, it was clear that all major obstacles had been removed and all of Ikast's ten bus lines would go full fare-free and permanently from the start of the new timetable in August 1998.⁴⁶ The reasons behind the decision were primarily financial.⁴⁷ At the time, the budget for PT in Ikast was 3.2 mill. DKK and it was never something the municipality had earned money on. It was reckoned that the municipality would lose out on an income from fares of c. 10,000-12,000 DKK per year, but this would be outweighed by money saved on administration and on maintaining a functioning ticket system (incl. the replacement of the old system). A crucial component in the change was that the municipality had been able to cut a deal with Ringkjøbing Amt which meant that "amtet" would contribute eighty per cent of the price of a bus ticket for students attending its high school ("amts-gymnasiet") and business school

⁴¹ *Midtjyllands Avis*, "Fortsat Gratis-Bus og Steward i Ikast."

⁴² *Midtjyllands Avis*, "Fortsat Gratis-Bus og Steward i Ikast."

⁴³ *Midtjyllands Avis*, "Fortsat Gratis-Bus og Steward i Ikast."

⁴⁴ *Midtjyllands Avis*, "Gratis med Alle Busser", 9 September 1997, 16.

⁴⁵ *Midtjyllands Avis*, "Gratis med Alle Busser."

⁴⁶ It was widely reported at the time: Jan Bjerre Lauridsen, "Byens Gratis Bus", *Jyllands-Posten* 17 March 1998, 3; Ritzau, "Gratis Bybus I Ikast", 7 July 1998. The latter articles was reprinted around the same time in *Jydske Vestkysten*, *Løgstør Avis*, *Ringkjøbing Amts Dagblad*, *Aalborg Stiftstidende*.

⁴⁷ Marianne Harbo, "Gratis Busser til Borgerne Betaler Sig", *Berlingske* 31 January 1998, 3; Bjerre Lauridsen, "Byens Gratis Bus"; Rune Huvendick Jensen, "Kommune Sparer ved Gratis Kørsel."

(“handelskole”).⁴⁸ Again, it was noted that there had been a significant increase in passenger numbers, but that it had not been possible to move people from the car to the bus.⁴⁹ Chair of the technical and environmental committee, Ove Nørholm said that this was a part of the initiative that the municipality would continue to develop, but reminded everyone that “Ikast is a rural district. And we would have to expand the network enormously to be able to reach all those who drive a car today.”⁵⁰

6. Thirty Years of FFPT in Ikast(-Brande): Reflections on a Fare-Free Principle

It did not take long before the FFPT system in the old Ikast municipality was declared a success. It is difficult to claim otherwise now. By August 2024, the municipality will have had FFPT for thirty years, and for at least nineteen of those it has been entirely fare-free.⁵¹ This is not to say that the running of the system has been unproblematic. As the following discussion reveals, there have been challenges along the way, some of a serious nature, and the viability of the system is under regular evaluation. But it still runs. It is not the explicit aim of this report to explain why FFPT has been a success in Ikast-Brande, although it can be claimed that some of the issues discussed contribute to the system’s survival. The aim of the section is instead to discuss issues that have arisen from the analysis of the gathered material. These issues can be said to hold prominence in the material in the sense that they have either kept reappearing or been the focus of particular attention at a particular time. In short, the issues evolve around the following

perspectives: (1) political and administrative; (2) economic; (3) social; (4) environmental; and (5) influence and applicability. The focus is primarily on the time following the introduction of full FFPT, but references to the period between 1994 and 1998 are made. In discussing each issue, the thematic nature of the argument is central, but I have looked to keep the chronology clear and tried to avoid anachronisms.

6.1 Political and Administrative Perspectives

It is worth noticing that politicians in Ikast-Brande tend to describe the municipality’s FFPT system as a fare-free principle. Already in February 1995, when a partial system had only been tested for about seven months, then mayor Kjeld Broberg Lind used the phrase, remarking that although everyone was pleased, it was uncertain whether the “fare-free principle can continue.”⁵² Since, local politicians have continued to refer to the system as such, a fare-free principle.⁵³ Given the recurring usage, the choice of phrase is hardly coincidental and, I think, it points to something fundamental about the nature of FFPT in Ikast-Brande. It implies that it is not prescribed by law that Ikast-Brande shall have FFPT. The universal service obligation commits the municipality legally to provide transportation for certain parts of the population, but it does not dictate that it should be done within a fare-free system. That is a decision made by politicians in the municipality in collaboration with Midttrafik. It is regularly under scrutiny and can be altered should political priorities change.

It follows that the fare-free principle must have political support in the municipality. This seems to have been the case for most of its existence.

⁴⁸ Marianne Harbo, “Gratis Busser til Borgerne Betalers Sig”; Bjerre Lauridsen, “Byens Gratis Bus.”

⁴⁹ Bjerre Lauridsen, “Byens Gratis Bus”; Huvendick Jensen, “Kommune Sparer ved Gratis Kørsel.”

⁵⁰ Huvendick Jensen, “Kommune Sparer ved Gratis Kørsel.”

⁵¹ As mentioned, there are now two so-called “closed routes” in Ikast-Brande. These have been running since 2016. The reasons for their existence will be discussed later in this section.

⁵² *Herning Folkeblad*, “Næsten for Populær.”

⁵³ E.g.: *Midtjyllands Avis*, “Lettere at Komme til Ikast”, 28 February 1997, 24; *Ritzau*, “Gratis Busser til Alle”, 17 August 2003, 3 (this article was reprinted on the following day in *Berlingske*, *Århus Stiftstidende*, *Lolland-Falsters Folketidende*, *Frederiksborg Amts Avis*, *MetroXpress* and *Fyens Stiftstidende*); *Midtjyllands Avis*, “Byrådet Vil Holde på De Unge med Busser”, 6 February 2007, 5; Søren Bagge, “Justeringer for Buskørsel”, *Vejle Amts Folkeblad* 13 June 2007, 18.

More precisely, the FFPT system seems to have endured due to broad political support rather than the continued dominance of certain groupings. Traditionally, Ikast-Brande votes on the right side of the political spectrum. Since the municipal reform in 2007, the municipality has had two mayors, Carsten Kissmeyer and Ib Boye Lauritsen, both coming from what has long been the country's largest conservative-liberal and agrarian party, Venstre.⁵⁴ Prior to the reform, the mayors of Ikast, Brande and Nørre Snede tended to come from Venstre and other similar parties. It cannot be denied that the priorities of the political right can be detected in the arguments in favour of the fare-free principle. In the 1990s, financial feasibility (as opposed to e.g. environmental concerns) was decisive in the establishment and expansion of the FFPT system and, as will be discussed later, it has been the most important factor since. But, the survival of FFPT in Ikast-Brande has been due to support across traditional political faultlines. In 2011, for example, when a drastic increase in the number of passengers required the municipality to find extra funds for the running of the system at a time when cutbacks had been planned, Frank Heideman Sørensen from the Social Democrats emphasised that the fare-free principle was supported by the entire city council.⁵⁵ The statement is indicative of the networks' history in general. The political support has been broad, except on a few more or less notable occasions.

The fare-free principle is under regular political scrutiny. For example, it is evaluated every time a new process of licitation on the running of PT in the municipality comes

around.⁵⁶ Generally, the political support is there, although individual politicians and parties have declared themselves to hold different priorities from time to time.⁵⁷ Arguably, the biggest threat to the fare-free principle came with the municipal reform in 2007. It is worth taking a closer look at the implications of the reform and discussions surrounding its implementation, because they illustrate how radical administrative changes destabilised political support. In addition, they show that the fare-free principle relies on a certain amount of goodwill higher up in the system.

As discussed, there were certain felicitous conditions that made the introduction of FFPT in the old Ikast municipality possible. One was that PT was organised differently in Ringkjøbing Amt than in other parts of Denmark. The municipal reform that came into effect in 2007 changed the country's administrative landscape significantly. Among other things, it replaced the thirteen old "amter" with five "regions", each of which should run its own PT company. The new Ikast-Brande municipality became part of the Central Denmark Region whose PT company became Midttrafik. The introduction of the new structure threatened the existence of the FFPT system for a couple of reasons.⁵⁸ First, the reform placed the responsibility for running PT within the regions entirely in the hands of new regional companies, including Midttrafik. Second, it was only Ikast who had a fare-free principle prior to the reform – Brande and Nørre Snede did not – so it was necessary to consider whether the FFPT system was something the

⁵⁴ "Venstre" means "left" in Danish, a somewhat ironic fact of this otherwise right-leaning party. The reason is found in the early history of the party. In the nineteenth century it was part of the liberal left in Danish politics. During the twentieth century, it gradually moved right along the political spectrum.

⁵⁵ Mikael Lund, "Buskørsel Drukner i Succes", *Ikast Avis* 14 December 2011, 4.

⁵⁶ E.g. Ritzau, "Gratis Busser til Alle"; Mikkel Korsgaard Christensen, "Samkørsel Er Det Eneste Rigtige, Indtil Delebilerne Kommer", *Herning Folkeblad* 7 October 2019, 20; Michael Holmgaard Christiansen, "Hvor Svært Er Det at Tage Toget på Arbejde?", *Herning Folkeblad* 11 November 2021, 20.

⁵⁷ In 2002, for example, after decisions to make cuts in the PT budget, there were splits within Venstre and other parts of the municipal council about whether this should cause the FFPT system to be discontinued (Hans Jørgen Hansen, "Klar til at Opgive Gratis Busser", *Midtjyllands Avis* 24 April 2002, 11). In 2005, the Socialist People's Party's ("Socialistisk Folkeparti") candidate stated that she did not think the FFPT was financially feasible any longer and declared that she prioritised childcare (Henrik Schulz, "Nørre Snede Integrerer Bedre End Ikast", *Herning Folkeblad* 12 November 2005, 23); In 2009, a candidate from the Danish People's Party ("Dansk Folkeparti") argued for dropping the FFPT system and investing in better bicycle lanes instead (Jørn Roed, "Drop Gratis-Busserne og Lav Gode Cykelstier", *Herning Folkeblad* 28 May 2009, 12).

⁵⁸ Henrik Øster-Jørgensen, "Slut med Gratis Busser i Ikast", *Herning Folkeblad* 2 June 2005, 9.

new larger municipality wanted. In other words, the FFPT system needed to be discussed among the three old municipalities as well as at a regional level.

Already in 2005, as the shape of the new regions was beginning to settle, it became clear that Midttrafik would be a threat to Ikast's fare-free principle. The law removed municipalities' freedom to determine fare structures and placed it entirely in the hands of the new regional companies; it was now them that set the rules.⁵⁹ The only exception: municipalities were allowed to run their own bus routes provided they were restricted to the transportation of schoolchildren.⁶⁰ In the spring of 2006, the new Ikast-Brande municipality declared that it was not interested in taking advantage of this exception: Kissmeyer described it as "unthinkable."⁶¹ In other words, if the fare-free principle was to continue, it relied on the negotiation of deal with Midttrafik. In the autumn of 2007, eventually, an agreement was reached with Midttrafik that gave the new municipality the freedom to continue a FFPT system similar to the one that had existed in the old Ikast municipality.⁶² The decision to pursue such an agreement came after lengthy discussions between politicians from Ikast, Brande and Nørre Snede. Although, ultimately, the conclusion was in favour of retaining the fare-free principle in the new municipality, the debates revealed fractures in the broad political support that has otherwise characterised the system.

In the discussions leading up to the merger of Ikast, Brande and Nørre Snede on 1 January 2007, PT was an important topic.⁶³ Generally, there was broad political support for continuing Ikast's fare-free principle and expanding it to include the entire area of the new municipality.⁶⁴ However, some leading politicians, including Kissmeyer, were hesitant and criticised from several directions for being unwilling to fight for the survival of the fare-free principle.⁶⁵ The discussions weighed social cohesion against financial feasibility. For example, Evald Asp from the Social Democrats stressed that "it is extremely important for our municipality that we will be tied together by good bus connections."⁶⁶ And Karen Skyum from the Danish Social Liberal Party ("Radikale Venstre") agreed. "We are in a situation," she said, "where we ought to say that that [FFPT] is something we want to pay for. It is important that the new municipality is properly tied together."⁶⁷ Kissmeyer and his colleagues from Venstre, were more cautious. The former mayor of Nørre Snede and upcoming chair of the technical and environmental committee, Uffe Henneberg argued that "it is obvious that we must have good bus connections for the municipality to hang together. But we have to make calculations and see how things develop."⁶⁸ Ultimately, he said, "it will be decided by crowns and pennies whether it is possible to

⁵⁹ Rudi Holm, "Slut med Gratis Buskørsel", *Nyhedsmagasinet Danske Kommuner* 2 June 2005; Øster-Jørgensen, "Slut med Gratis Busser."

⁶⁰ *Midtjyllands Avis*, "Gratis Busser Stopper Nok", 22 March 2006, 9.

⁶¹ *Midtjyllands Avis*, "Gratis Busser Stopper Nok."

⁶² E.g. Søren Bagge, "Gratis Busser for Alle", *Vejle Amts Folkeblad* 11 June 2007, 19; Søren Bagge, "Justeringer for Buskørsel"; *Horsens Folkeblad*, "Gule og Blå Busser", 28 June 2007, 10.

⁶³ E.g. Karen Krautwald, "Ældre Er Frygteligt Beskedne", *Vejle Amts Folkeblad* 10 November 2005, 23; Henrik Øster-Jørgensen, "Det Trafikale Helvede", *Herning Folkeblad* 1 June 2006, 13.

⁶⁴ E.g. Jakob Holm, "Æggekage og Debat", *Herning Folkeblad* 27 October 2005, 12; Søren Bagge, "Alle Vil Det Bedste for Alle", *Vejle Amts Folkeblad* 3 November 2005, 21; Jens Amtoft, "Politikere Enige om Samarbejde", *Horsens Folkeblad* 4 November 2005, 12.

⁶⁵ Henrik Øster-Jørgensen, "Byrådet Er en Lukket Fest", *Herning Folkeblad* 24 March 2006, 10; Hans Jørgen Hansen, "Langt Mellem Busser", *Midtjyllands Avis* 24 March 2006, 11.

⁶⁶ Hans Jørgen Hansen, "Langt Mellem Busser."

⁶⁷ Kim Kristensen, "Vil Slås for Gratis-Bussen", *Herning Folkeblad* 27 April 2006, 12.

⁶⁸ Karen Krautwald, "Offentlig Transport Mod Øst", *Vejle Amts Folkeblad* 24 March 2006, 18.

have that [FFPT] system.”⁶⁹ When, eventually, it was decided to continue the fare-free principle in the new Ikast-Brande municipality, it did come with an extra cost of 2 mill. DKK. Kissmeyer conceded that the money had been granted because “we wish to tie the municipality together, so that it is possible to get around even for those who don’t have their own transport”, but he was also quick to underline that “this is very much about handling things practically”, it “should not be seen as the great CO₂-initiative or transportation policy initiative.”⁷⁰

The fare-free principle in Ikast-Brande relies on political support and, generally, that has been broad and persistent. When it came under pressure during the municipal reform, schisms became noticeable, revealing how far politicians were willing to go to maintain FFPT and under what circumstances. The discussions highlighted the two most important considerations behind the fare-free principle: financial feasibility and social cohesion. These will be discussed in the following sections.

6.2 Economic Perspectives

The most important consideration behind the fare-free principle in Ikast-Brande is economical. The previous section highlights that it is also fulfils a social function and, as will be discussed later, politicians within the municipality have not been blind to the fact that FFPT pertains to environmental questions as well. However, the economy has been granted the greatest significance. It will be recalled that economic considerations were central to the introduction of FFPT in the old Ikast municipality. The transportation trials initiated by the Ministry of Traffic in the early 1990s

looked to increase economic efficiency and the authorities in Ikast quickly realised that, basically, it was more expensive for them run a PT system that collected fares than one that did not. The income lost from ticket sales was outweighed by less maintenance and administration. Essentially, this has been the main argument since.

This is not to say, of course, that the financial state of the FFPT system has remained static, only that the conclusion has remained the same. As already pointed out, the fare-free principle is tested every time a process of licitation on the running of PT in the municipality comes around. In addition, the material studied here illustrates that several factors can threaten the financial stability that underpins the fare-free principle. A large, national municipal reform is one example. Another, also coming top-down, is when the government decides to put a stop to certain subsidies.⁷¹ At a lower level, changes within the municipality can have an effect on the economic sustainability of FFPT. In 2011, for instance, the municipal authorities had to deal with the financial consequences of having both too few passengers and too many. In March, they announced a reduction in the number of routes, because the buses did not carry enough passengers.⁷² When the number of passengers was below five, the price per passenger was too high. In December, the municipality had to contend with a dramatic increase in the number of passengers.⁷³ At a time when savings had been planned, the municipality had to direct more funds to its FFPT network. Other issues that affect the financial stability of the fare-free principle have been: the renewal of vehicles and increases in fuel expenses.⁷⁴

⁶⁹ Øster-Jørgensen, “Byrådet Er en Lukket Fest”; Hansen, “Langt Melleml Busser.”

⁷⁰ Ritzau, “Ikast-Brande Udvider Gratis Buskørsel”, 6 October 2007. The decision as well as Kissmeyer’s words was reported in several newspapers and outlets during the following days, e.g. in *TV2, Nordjyske Stiftstidende, Thisted Dagblad* and *Fyens Stiftstidende*.

⁷¹ Ritzau, “Gratis Busser til Alle.”

⁷² *Horsens Folkeblad*, “Busser Får Færre Afgange – Klovborg Mister Rute”, 5 March 2011.

⁷³ Lund, “Buskørsel Drukner i Succes”; Lennart Poulsen, “Medaljens Bagside”, *Herning Folkeblad* 17 December 2011, 18. Similar issues occurred in 2001 and 2009: *Midtjyllands Avis*, “For Lidt Penge til Buskørsel”, 12 December 2001, 12; *Vejle Amts Folkeblad*, “Ekstra Bus fra Blåhøj”, 31 August 2009.

⁷⁴ Korsgaard Christensen, ”Samkørsel Er Det Eneste Rigtige”; Holmgaard Christiansen, ”Hvor Svært Er Det”; Laila Kempel, “Dyrt at Køre med Busser”, *Ikast Avis* 29 August 2012, 14; Laila Kempel, “Det Er Ikke Gratis at Have Gratis-Busser”, *Ikast Avis* 22 January 2014, 13.

6.3 Social Perspectives

Although the economic argument holds sway, the social aspect of the fare-free principle is important. This became visible during the debates surrounding the 2007 municipal reform where FFPT was seen as a crucial way of maintaining social cohesion within the municipality. It is worth remembering here that when politicians talked about binding the new municipality together via FFPT, it was not a question that directly concerned everyone. As discussed, from the beginning, the FFPT system has been closely linked to the universal service obligation. It is tied in with the municipality's legal obligations and mainly services certain population groups, primarily schoolchildren and the elderly. In other words, as Morten Marott Larsen from the Danish Board of Technology ("Teknologirådet") said to the newspaper *Information* when, in 2008, the Lemvig municipality (about eighty kilometres west of Ikast-Brande) began trialling a FFPT system of its own, this is essentially about "social redistribution in society" since "it is typically low-income groups who use public transport, it will mostly benefit them, if it's free."⁷⁵

Although the fare-free principle is universal in its aim, it mainly concerns certain societal groups, particularly those identified by the universal service obligation. This has also

meant that certain groups have been excluded. As mentioned, the timetables are predominantly tailored to suit the needs of the children and youth who attend the municipality's educational institutions. This can be detected in the departure times as well as in the geography of the routes. Occasionally, the sufficiency of these come up for debate and the need for adjustments are considered.⁷⁶ But, at times, the municipal authorities have also shown themselves unwilling to go beyond the dictates of the universal service obligation. In 2013, for example, they stressed that the FFPT system was designed to cater the needs of children attending public schools in the municipality.⁷⁷ Charter schools ("friskoler") were not included in the universal service obligation and, therefore, the authorities were unwilling to adjust routes to facilitate pupils in such institutions. Similarly, the municipal authorities have felt compelled to place restrictions on the fare-free principle. The cause was the asylum centre Kærshovedgård, situated about ten kilometres south of Bording.⁷⁸ By 2016, the number of asylum seekers using the FFPT system had led to complaints within the municipality: pupils and their families felt unsafe.⁷⁹ The municipality responded by turning the two routes that went past

⁷⁵ Marie Varming, "Det Bliver Gratis at Tage Bussen i Lemvig", *Information* 1 August 2008, 4-5.

⁷⁶ E.g. Uffe Henneberg, "Ny Lokal Gratis Busrute i Nørre-Snedemrødet", *Ikast Avis* 18 June 2008, 14; Søren Bagge, "Ny Skolebus fra Klovborg til Ikast", *Vejle Amts Folkeblad* 16 June 2008, 20; Nina Hansen, "Bustider får Branditter til at Fravælge Gymnasiet i Ikast", *Herning Folkeblad* 11 November 2010, 17; Poulsen, "Medaljens Bagside."

⁷⁷ Thomas Vang Nielsen, "Nej til Kommunale Skolebusser til Friskoler", *Herning Folkeblad* 13 March 2013, 14.

⁷⁸ Kærshovedgård is a so-called departure centre ("udrejsecenter") for asylum seekers. It is one of two such centres in Denmark that are primarily dedicated to asylum seekers who have been rejected for asylum and are awaiting deportation. The centre is highly controversial, partly because the conditions are poor and partly because it mixes criminals (e.g. people convicted for terrorism) with normal asylum seekers. As late as April 2024, a Parliament Ombudsman visited the centre and although it was concluded that Kærshovedgård is not in violation with the United Nations Convention Against Torture or the European Convention on Human Rights, it was reported that conditions were unsafe and had worsened since the last visit in 2017 (Birgitte Skovlund Asmussen, "Folketingets Ombudsmand Har Besøgt Omstridt Udrejsecenter: 'Utrygge' og 'Meget Belastende' Forhold", *Danmarks Radio* 27 April 2024, <https://www.dr.dk/nyheder/indland/forraelse-stofmisbrug-og-utryghed-praeger-udrejsecenter-kaershovedgaard-mere-end> (accessed 28 May 2024).

⁷⁹ E.g. Natacha Tjørnholt, "OK at Lukke Skolebussen for Afvist Asylansøgere", *Danmarks Radio* 7 July 2016; Camilla Bøgeholt Lund and Julie Øjersén Frederiksen, "Udrejsecenter Skaber Stadig Utryghed i Lokalområdet: Lokal Tager Sagen i Egen Hånd", *B.T.* 18 September 2021 <https://www.bt.dk/samfund/udrejsecenter-skaber-stadig-utryghed-i-lokalomraadet-lokal-tager-sagen-i-egen> (accessed 28 May 2024); Ole Tranberg, "Læserbrev: Skal Udrejsecenter Kærshovedgård Også Være Utåleligt for Borgerne?", *Ikast-Brandenytt.dk* 4 January 2016 <https://www.ikast-brandenytt.dk/artikel/5eaada1f-67c8-4423-989f-56838eb44127> (accessed 28 May 2024).

Kærshovedgård into “closed school routes.”⁸⁰ These now only accepted schoolchildren as passengers and thus, essentially, Ikast-Brandø’s FFPT system went from a full one to a partial. On the occasion, Kissmeyer said that “if the asylum seekers need transportation, it has to be a matter for the state, so I don’t have bad conscience.”⁸¹ He was backed up by Minister for Integration, Inger Støjberg, who stated that “a municipality can choose that it is only some of the municipality’s school buses that are open to other passengers.”⁸²

The issues surrounding Kærshovedgård concern some of the larger social issues associated with the FFPT network, but they also point to smaller ones such as what it is like for passengers to use FFPT in Ikast-Brandø. The material analysed here predominantly touch upon larger, structural issues, but, occasionally, there have been reports and articles that have interviewed passengers and asked them about their experiences. From a research perspective, they must be considered anecdotal in nature. Nevertheless, it seems worthwhile to draw attention to a couple of these articles. In 2003, for example, a reporter from *Herning Folkeblad* travelled on one of the city buses in Ikast, reporting how one passenger, Tove Petersen, was pleased with the fare-free buses because, otherwise, she would find it hard to get to work.⁸³ Tove Petersen also emphasised her conversations with the bus steward, Sonja Sørensen. With her “cucumbers and tomatoes are discussed in the same way as with friends and family” and Sørensen added about her interactions with other passengers: “I hear a lot of things and I clearly have a social function for many passengers. From time to time, we have experienced that some elderly make the journey for fun, because they need to talk to someone. And that is totally fine.”⁸⁴ An episode of the

popular Danish documentary series *Gintberg på Kanten* (“Gintberg on the Edge”) reveals similar tendencies.⁸⁵ The program visited Ikast-Brandø in 2012 and one segment of the episode was dedicated to the municipality’s FFPT system. Here the show’s host, the stand-up comedian Jan Gintberg, takes a ride on a city bus in Ikast, interacting with the passengers and the bus driver, Anette Laursen. Here Gintberg notices that Anette Laursen has received a flower from one of the passengers which leads to the following exchange:

Gintberg: Anette? Can I ask, I saw this Poinsettia here, who has got ... is it one you have received?

Laursen: It is one I got from one of the regulars.

G: That would never have happened in Copenhagen, I can promise you that.

L: No, it’s probably good that we live here.

G: There you would have a brick through the window, I can tell you.⁸⁶

Gintberg’s jokes aside, the flower suggests a somewhat unusual level of intimacy between passengers and personnel. A conversation Gintberg has with an elderly woman indicate that the bus is a safe place:

Woman: I could use a bus in the evening.

Gintberg: Oh, a nightbus.

W: Yes, an evening bus. Just an evening bus.

⁸⁰ These are routes no. 173 and no. 180

⁸¹ Tjørnholm, “OK at Lukke Skolebussen.”

⁸² Tjørnholm, “OK at Lukke Skolebussen.” Støjberg’s full title was Minister for Immigration, Integration and Housing.

⁸³ Niels Henrik Sørensen, “Bybus med Social Funktion”, *Herning Folkeblad* 15 September 2003.

⁸⁴ Sørensen, “Bybus med Social Funktion.”

⁸⁵ *Gintberg på Kanten* is produced by the national public channel *Danmarks Radio* (DR). It started in 2011 and the latest season (no.9) aired in 2023. Ikast-Brandø’s FFPT system features in episode seven in season three. The episode is entitled “The Municipality” (“Kommunen”). It aired on 20 December 2012.

⁸⁶ *Gintberg på Kanten*, “Kommunen”, *Danmarks Radio* 20 December 2012, 08:55-12:04, https://www.dr.dk/drtv/se/gintberg-paa-kanten_-kommunen_52551 (accessed 30 May 2024).

G: So if there had been a free bus in the evening too, you would have gone more to rock and roll?

W: Listen, we have many lonely people here in Ikast who sits ... and are afraid to go out as soon as it gets dark.

G: I see.

W: Yes.

G: Afraid of?

W: Well, that I don't have to say, but one hears so much.

G: [doubting attitude] Aah, in Ikast? I can understand it on Nørrebro.⁸⁷

W: Yes, you can tell me. Do you think we're behind here?

G: [doubting attitude] Aaa... there can't be much happening ...

W: [interrupts] No, I can tell you.

G: Is there a lot of trouble in this municipality?

W: There can be. Yes, there can be.⁸⁸

While these interview say something about the experiences of using FFPT in Ikast-Brandø, it can be noted that Anette Laursen does not think the fare-free system of much relevance in this respect:

Gintberg: What do you think would happen if you ... if you... if you put down... said it would cost twenty kroner for a ride?

Laursen: I don't think it would make a difference.

G: [surprised] You don't think it would make a difference?

L: No.⁸⁹

6.4 Environmental Perspectives

When, on the eve of the municipal reform in 2007, Kissmeyer emphasised that the FFPT system “should not be seen as the great CO₂-initiative or transportation policy initiative”, it is not unlikely that he wished to reassure his constituents about the nature of the policies he was helping to push through.⁹⁰ Traditionally, his party, Venstre, have not been the most environmentally progressive. But, probably, he spoke from experience; from what he knew about FFPT in the old Ikast municipality: from an environmental perspective, it had made little difference.

As discussed, the nationwide trials that led to the introduction of FFPT in Ikast had secondary objectives related to environmental issues. In addition to testing the economic benefits of the initiatives, it also looked to examine whether they would cause car drivers to use PT more. In February 1995, the planner of the municipality's technical department, Niels Peter Mohr, stated that in this respect the trial supported many of the schemes they were working on, including “more environmentally conscious transport policies, in line with the idea of the Green City.”⁹¹ It will be recalled that Mohr's initial estimate of the system's success proved too optimistic when it came to the number of car users it had shifted on to PT. Later, as the transfer to full FFPT was being decided, then chair of the technical and environmental committee Ove Nørholm repeated that fact while underlining that “it was part of the original idea” and it was not abandoned: “work on that continues.”⁹² At the same time, Nørholm also drew attention to some of the difficulties the municipality faced in achieving such aims. “You have to remember,” he said, “that Ikast is a rural district. And we have to expand the network enormously to reach all those who use a car today.”⁹³ When the Ministry of Traffic

⁸⁷ Area with rough reputation in central Copenhagen.

⁸⁸ *Gintberg på Kanten*, “Kommunen”, 08:55-12:04.

⁸⁹ *Gintberg på Kanten*, “Kommunen”, 08:55-12:04.

⁹⁰ *Ritzau*, “Ikast-Brandø Udvider”.

⁹¹ *Herning Folkeblad*, “Gratis med Bybussen.”

⁹² Huvendick Jensen, “Kommune Sparer.”

⁹³ Huvendick Jensen, “Kommune Sparer.”

published its partial evaluation of the trials, it agreed with Nørholm, concluding that a FFPT system cannot “change the energy and environmental situation radically” in the sense of moving car users on to PT; for many in rural areas, the car is “an inextricable part of everyday life.”⁹⁴

In 2019, a member of the construction and technical committee (“bygge- og teknikudvalget”) in Ikast-Brande, Birthe Sørensen, said that the FFPT system had led many car drivers to take the bus. “We can clearly feel that there has become fewer cars in the city centre”: “it means less CO2-pollution and that is good for the climate.”⁹⁵ The statement echoes Mohr’s assessment from 1995 and seems equally inaccurate. The material studied here indicate that in this respect the situation has not changed dramatically. Even after thirty years of FFPT, it has not shifted more car drivers on to PT. Soon after, Birthe Sørensen was contradicted by Henrik Engedahl, then chair of the technical and environmental committee. Engedahl stated that “I can’t in that way collect any climate-goodwill on that account” and in doing so only repeated what seems to have been the general view within the municipality since the introduction of FFPT.⁹⁶ In 2015, Kissmeyer repeated his earlier statement that in his municipality there was nothing to be gained from FFPT on the environmental front, adding rather emphatically that there the car is “the best and the most environmentally friendly solution.”⁹⁷ His point was that a PT network large and flexible enough to address peoples’ needs, would run empty most of the time and therefore cause greater damage to the environment.

This is not to say that, recently, the municipality has been oblivious to environmental concerns relating to its FFPT network. It is only that the idea that it might lead car drivers on to PT is thoroughly debunked. Instead, the municipality focuses on, for example, its buses. In 2019, Engedahl noted that they ranked low on the Euronorm scale and when the next tender was to take place (2022), it would have to be decided whether the municipality wished to improve on that.⁹⁸

6.5 Perspectives on Influence and Applicability

As mentioned, it is hard to deny that the FFPT system in Ikast-Brande has been a success. Besides its longevity, another indication is the fact that, in the time since its inception, the municipality has been a constant point of reference every time the topic of FFPT crops up in the Danish media. In a sense, the FFPT system can be said to have put the municipality on the map. This is not to say that everyone in Denmark immediately thinks of FFPT when they hear the words “Ikast-Brande.” Probably, many will rather associate the municipality with its sports teams and athletes (handball and football, especially), the Klovborg cheese, the clothing company *Bestseller* whose brands include, for instance, *Jack & Jones* and *Vero Moda* and the 320 metres high-rise building that its owners proposed to build in Brande in the late 2010s.⁹⁹ But for those interested in the structures of PT fare policies in Denmark, it can hardly have skipped notice.

Arguably, the material studied for this report gives a good indication of the FFPT system’s influence and reputation. It consists primarily of regional newspapers from the area around

⁹⁴ *Trafikministeriet*, “Trafikken på Landet”, 153.

⁹⁵ *Arbejderen*, “Minister Skal Tjekke Fordele ved Gratis Kollektiv Transport”, 4 September 2019.

⁹⁶ Korsgaard Christensen, “Samkørsel Er Det Eneste Rigtige.”

⁹⁷ Rasmus Walther Jensen, “Kommune: Gratis Busser Giver Ikke Flere Passagerer”, *Berlingske* 4 June 2015.

⁹⁸ Korsgaard Christensen, “Samkørsel Er Det Eneste Rigtige.”

⁹⁹ The project carried the name “The Bestseller Tower” (“Bestseller-tårnet”) and “Bestseller Village.” Despite being approved by the municipal authorities in 2019, the project did not start and was eventually dropped in 2020. The fact that the building would have been the highest in Western Europe and placed in a city of only 7,000 inhabitants, meant that it drew a lot of national and international attention. For example: Richard Orange, “‘Like the Eye of Sauron’: Western Europe’s Tallest Building Planned for a Tiny Danish Town” *Guardian* 1 April 2019. <https://www.theguardian.com/cities/2019/apr/01/like-the-eye-of-sauron-western-europes-tallest-building-planned-for-tiny-danish-town-brande-bestseller> (accessed 28 May 2024).

Ikast-Brande (e.g. *Herning Folkeblad* and *Midtjyllands Avis*). But there is also a significant number of articles published in national newspapers such as *Politiken*, *Berlingske* and *Jyllands-Posten* and, as highlighted already, the FFPT system has also featured in popular national television programmes such as *Go' Morgen Danmark* (“Good Morning Denmark”) and *Gintberg på Kanten*.¹⁰⁰ Looking at the political levels at which the system have been discussed, a similar picture emerges. Born out of a transport initiative initiated and supported by the Ministry of Traffic, the FFPT system was naturally of interest at a high political level in the years immediately following its introduction. Since, it has only occasionally been the subject of interest from politicians working in Parliament. In 2019, for example, the then newly elected environmental and energy spokesperson for the Danish People’s Party (“Dansk Folkeparti”), Morten Messerschmidt, petitioned the Ministry of Transport to examine what it would cost to introduce FFPT in Denmark’s four largest cities.¹⁰¹ Supported by other parties in Parliament – for instance, the Unity List (“Enhedslisten”) – the petition was inspired by the introduction of FFPT in Luxembourg as well as a knowledge of the existence of several FFPT systems in municipalities across Denmark, including Ikast-Brande. Messerschmidt’s idea was that it could help shift car drivers on to PT thus solving congestion and environmental problems in the

larger cities. Eventually, the calculations the Ministry of Transport received from the Technical University of Denmark were not encouraging: it would be expensive and most likely not have the desired effects.¹⁰² (A conclusion that correlated well with the experiences made in Ikast-Brande.) Examples such as this one are few and far between, however.¹⁰³ It is at lower political levels that Ikast-Brande’s influence and reputation has been most noticeable, at least when it comes to the question of PT fare policies.

Today, Ikast-Brande is not the only place in Denmark with FFPT (Figure 3).¹⁰⁴ (Figure 3 can be contrasted with Figure 4, an overview published in *Midtjyllands Avis* in 2009 in connection with the introduction of FFPT in the Morsø municipality.)¹⁰⁵ But, at least to my knowledge, Ikast-Brande was the first place in Denmark to implement full FFPT. The other municipalities with FFPT are fairly similar to Ikast-Brande: rural, not densely populated and, of course, required by the universal service obligation to offer PT to its children and elderly. In several of these municipalities, Ikast-Brande seems to have been an inspiration. Arguably, the most noticeable other example is the Lemvig municipality whose FFPT system dates back to 2008 and seems to have been introduced with more than a mere glance at how PT was organised not far east from there, in Ikast-Brande.¹⁰⁶ Furthermore, Ikast-Brande has also been a point of reference in numerous municipalities where FFPT has been considered

¹⁰⁰ *Go' Morgen Danmark* is a morning television on the national public channel TV2. It has been running since 1996. Gunnar Jakobsen, then chair of the technical and environmental committee, appeared on *Go' Morgen Danmark* in January 1997 to discuss the municipality’s FFPT system (*Herning Folkeblad*, “Gadespejlet”, 18 January 1997, 8).

¹⁰¹ *Arbejderen*, “Minister Skal Tjekke.” Messerschmidt is one of the most renowned politicians on the political right in Denmark. He has served in Parliament from 2005-2009 and 2019 to the present. He was a member of the European Parliament from 2009-2019. He has been leader of the Danish People’s Party since 2022.

¹⁰² *Ingeniøren*, “DF’er om Gratis Offentlig Transport: Overrasket Over at Det Ikke Flytter Flere Bilister”, 20 February 2020; Louis Beck Petersen, “Gratis Kollektiv Trafik Har Lange Udsigter” *Ritzau* 1 March 2020.

¹⁰³ In 2015, the question of FFPT featured strongly in the agenda of the party “The Alternative” (“Alternativet”) (Walther Jensen, “Kommune: Gratis Busser.”). It was apparently also discussed in Parliament’s opening debate in 2017 (*Arbejderen*, “Minister Skal Tjekke”).

¹⁰⁴ Figure 3 is reasonably comprehensive when it comes to full FFPT systems. However, the landscape of partial systems is more complicated and it cannot be denied that the map lacks in this respect. The most notable partial systems are included.

¹⁰⁵ *Midtjyllands Avis*, “Busturen Bliver Gratis på Landet”, 18 February 2009, 5.

¹⁰⁶ E.g. Lars Kamstrup, “Gratis at Tage Bussen”, *Dagbladet Holstebro-Struer* 14 May 2008, 21; Varming, “Det Bliver Gratis”.

Figure 3. Map of FFPT systems in Denmark in 2024. The darker municipalities have full FFPT while the lighter run a partial system (of one kind or another). The year(s) indicate roughly when the system was introduced. If marked by an asterisks, it was first introduced in a municipality that existed prior to the municipal reform in 2007. All annotations are by the author. Source: Wikimedia Commons.

Figure 4. Map of FFPT systems in Denmark in 2009. Text (from top to bottom): “Free buses. Many municipalities are considering to offer the locals free buses. Here it has already been done. [map] [light grey] Free buses on the local routes in the municipality. [grey] Free school buses. [dark grey] Free service buses for senior citizens. Other solutions. Randers: Free buses for all senior citizens in the municipality. Aabenraa: Free bus card to all schoolchildren. Sønderborg: Free buses for all school children in the municipality and students under 25.” Source: *Midtjyllands Avis*, ”Busturen Bliver Gratis på Landet”, 18 February 2009, 5.

to a greater or lesser extent at one time or another, but, eventually, not implemented. These include: Aalborg (2002), Hadsten (2002), Hobro (2003), Vejle (2003), Odense (2003), Hjørring (2003, 2005), Viborg (2003, 2005), Skandeborg (2004), Fredericia (2004), Haslev (2004), Vissenbjerg (2004), Faaborg-Midtfyn (2005), Furesø (2005), Faxe (2005, 2021), Silkeborg (2007), Haderslev (2008), Ringsted (2008), Hedensted (2008), Horsens (2008), Bornholm (2009), Varde (2009), Århus (2012), Ringkøbing-Skjern (2014), Helsingør (2014, 2018) and Holstebro (2018).¹⁰⁷

To some extent, FFPT can be said to have put Ikast-Brande on the map. However, it could be argued that the municipality has been somewhat reticent when it comes to taking advantage of the system's publicity value, especially when compared to what has been done recently in places like Luxembourg and Tallinn. Overall, the municipal authorities appear to have been keen to discuss their fare-free principle when approached by the media and people from the outside, but little seems to have been done to promote the municipality on the basis of FFPT.¹⁰⁸ The material studied here shows that, occasionally, the idea has been raised, but, apart from a series of job adverts from the early 2000s, no substantial initiatives seems to have been undertaken.¹⁰⁹ And this seems unlikely to change. In the municipality's comprehensive

strategy for the coming years, "Vision 2030", FFPT is only mentioned briefly in the section pertaining to its policies as a rural district ("Landdistriktspolitik").¹¹⁰

That the fare-free principle should take up so little space in the municipality's official visions for the future, can seem curious. For instance, when in 2021, it was reported that the number of applicants for the municipality's high school, Ikast-Brande Gymnasium, had increased, FFPT was highlighted as one of its attractions.¹¹¹ Yet, it does not feature as part of the municipality's strategy for its youth and education.¹¹² The reasons for this and the general disinterestedness in furthering the municipality's image based on its FFPT system, is difficult to explain. But, it seems likely that it is linked to some of the issues discussed in this section. The authorities have consistently stressed that the municipality has a fare-free principle because it makes good economic sense. Occasionally, they have even shown themselves keen to dismiss positive knock-on effects. It will be recalled how, in 2007, following the municipal reform, Kissmeyer was adamant that the FFPT system "should not be seen as the great CO₂-initiative or transportation policy initiative" and, in 2019, Henrik Engedahl stressed that he could not "collect any climate-goodwill on that account."¹¹³ On the one hand, such statements

¹⁰⁷ The parentheses indicate the year in which discussions about FFPT has taken place and Ikast(-Brande) has been mentioned. The list is reasonably comprehensive. It is based on articles and reports about the possibility of introducing FFPT in these municipalities. The discussions vary in seriousness, but the list is focused on the involvement of politicians and other public officials. For example, readers' letters from private individuals are not included, but those attributed to people running for public office have. It must be noted that some of the municipalities (e.g. Haslev, Hobro, Vissenbjerg) disappeared with the municipal reform in 2007.

¹⁰⁸ It has often been reported that the municipality has been approached by other municipalities interested in the FFPT system (Øster-Jørgensen, "Slut med Gratis Busser." Apparently, there have also been visitors from Norway and Sweden (*Arbejderen*, "Gratis Busser Kan Betale Sig", 10 June 2004, 7).

¹⁰⁹ The question of why the city did not do more to increase its profile through FFPT was raised by Karen Skyum from the Danish Social Liberal Party ("Radikale Venstre") during a public debate in 2013 (Thomas Vang Nielsen, "Hvad Pokker Skal Man i Ikast-Brande", *Herning Folkeblad* 5 November 2013, 8). It also came up during a meeting about the municipality's business policies in 2009 (Laila Kempel, "Erhvervsfolket Vil Blande Sig", *Ikast Avis* 4 February 2009, 19). The job adverts concluded with a small notice: "In Ikast municipality there are 23,000 inhabitants out of which 13,000 live in the city of Ikast. In Ikast it is free to use the bus" (*Herning Folkeblad*, "Stillinger", 30 January 2002, 27; *Horsens Folkeblad*, "Stillinger", 2 February 2002, 7; *Midtjyllands Avis*, "Stillinger", 2 February 2002, 7; *Herning Folkeblad*, "Stillinger", 11 February 2004, 10).

¹¹⁰ For more, see: <https://ikast-brande.dk/politik/politikker-strategier-og-visioner>.

¹¹¹ *Herning Folkeblad*, "Flere Vil på Ikast-Brande Gymnasium", 9 March 2021, 13.

¹¹² For more, see: <https://ikast-brande.dk/politik/politikker-strategier-og-visioner>.

¹¹³ *Ritzau*, "Ikast-Brande Udvider"; Korsgaard Christensen, "Samkørsel Er Det Eneste Rigtige."

can be interpreted as speaking to the wishes of the largest part of the electorate. Politically, Ikast-Brande is predominately right-leaning. On the other, it can also be seen as simple honesty. From the very beginning, the municipal authorities have been forthright about their reasons for introducing and expanding FFPT – they have been economic – and they have consistently stressed that, most likely, their system is only feasible in similar municipalities. It is not applicable everywhere: as Kissmeyer has stressed on another occasion, “if you have a regular city-bus system where many people pay for tickets themselves, I would probably not recommend this [FFPT] solution.”¹¹⁴ In this light, it is perhaps not so curious that little has been done to promote the municipality based on its fare-free principle.

7. Conclusion

This report has examined the history and development of FFPT in the Danish municipality Ikast-Brande, what is often referred to as its “fare-free principle.” The report was commissioned by the LiFT project, because a questionnaire forwarded to the Ikast-Brande municipality was returned partially unanswered. The report does not provide answers to all the questions left ignored by the municipality, but it does throw light on a number of key issues. First, it outlines when and under what circumstances FFPT was introduced in the municipality. The cause was a series of nationwide transportation trials initiated by the Ministry of Traffic and conducted during the period 1992-1995. One of these was a one-year trial of a partial FFPT system in the old Ikast municipality. The trial proved so successful that the partial system was first made permanent in 1996 and then, in 1998, it was expanded to a full FFPT system. Second, the report clarifies what the reasons were behind the introduction of FFPT. These can be described as primarily economic and social. The nationwide trials aimed at improving the ways in which municipalities handled the universal service obligation. In other words, they looked to make the burden of this social obligation more financially efficient without loss in the quality of the service. That proved to

be the case with the FFPT system in the old Ikast municipality and the argument has not changed significantly since. It is cheaper for the municipality to fulfil its social obligations with a PT system that charges no fares from its passengers than with one that does. The economic and social arguments weigh heaviest in debates about Ikast-Brande’s FFPT system and it cannot be said to have had significant environmental effects. Particularly, it has not been able to shift car drivers on to PT, even after thirty years of operation.

In addition to providing answers to some of the questions looked for in the LiFT questionnaire, the studied materials brought out a number of other interesting issues. Of these, arguably, the following three stand out. First, the FFPT system is found in a municipality that, traditionally, belongs on the right side of the political spectrum. This can seem somewhat at odds with the image FFPT has today when, at least colloquially, it is often associated with the environmental and social politics of the political left. Perhaps, this is why politicians in the municipality have been keen to stress that their FFPT system is based predominately on economic considerations. Perhaps, it is also why they are not keen to promote the municipality based on its FFPT system. This concerns the second point of interest. FFPT can be said to have put Ikast(-Brande) on the map. It has featured consistently in debates about fare policies in Denmark over the past thirty years and seems to have had a distinct influence on the introduction of similar systems elsewhere in the country. Yet, little seems to have been done to promote the municipality based on its FFPT system. A curious fact considering the way FFPT systems are advertised in places like Luxembourg and Tallinn. Finally, it is interesting to note the extent and limitations of the FFPT system. It is there to fulfil a social function, but there are clear limits to how far the municipality is willing to go in that respect. The municipal authorities have proven themselves reluctant to move beyond the specific dictates of the universal service obligations. This means that, for example, school children attending charter schools are not catered by the system. It has also caused two routes to be closed for all passengers except school children. The

¹¹⁴ Jesper Munch Nielsen, “Politikere Overvejer at Indføre Gratis Buskørsel i Helsingør”, *Helsingør Dagblad* 9 April 2014, 6.

municipal authorities do not feel obliged to provide FFPT for asylum seekers and their visitors.

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